

Point-by-point reply to Santini et al.: Total population reports are necessary for global biomass estimation of wild mammals

A recent letter by Santini et al. (1) refers to our efforts to quantify mammal biomass globally (2). The letter by Santini et al. contains a long list of comments regarding our paper's methodology and main aim. Due to the short format permitted by the journal as a response to the letter, we provide a full point-by-point response below addressing all the criticisms raised.

The main aim of our original work was to estimate the combined global biomass of all ≈ 5000 mammal species together. To do so, we used dedicated RedList global population estimates. Santini et al. suggest instead to simply multiply locally-measured densities from their published dataset with range size to achieve global abundance estimates. When constructing our original manuscript, we indeed considered this approach and discussed it with Prof. Santini at the time. However we found that this approach yields clearly unrealistic results, as shown in Figure 1 of our response letter (also pasted here below). For example, applying their approach for the blue wildebeest (*Connochaetes taurinus*), one of the world's best monitored species, yields a global abundance estimate 10 times higher than the undisputed global values provided by experts over many years (≈ 20 million individuals using extrapolations from local densities vs. ≈ 2 based on expert knowledge regarding the total global population). The approach by Santini et al. provides similarly unrealistic results for many highly monitored species, as we show in our Fig. 1.

The letter by Santini et al., 2023 (1), is in black. We address each of their points below in blue.

Greenspoon et al. (1) used global population estimates of 392 mammal species to predict the global biomass of mammals. We caution against important limitations in their approach, which likely results in gross under-estimations of biomass and its uncertainty.

The authors derive $>97\%$ of their estimates from the IUCN RedList (RL) database, which is particularly ill-suited for this scope since it is compiled using different standards than scientific ecological investigation, and based on inconsistent approaches that are influenced by precautionary to evidentiary attitudes of different RL assessors (2). Because reliable population estimates are available only for relatively small areas (3), RL figures are generally obtained by summing up local estimates based on relatively scarce and biased data, including expert-based guesses with little supporting evidence (Table 1). Depending on the original purpose, RL figures might be over- or under-inflated (3, 4). Some RL's reported population sizes are derived by applying an average density across an area, which may not align with the area used in Greenspoon et al. to estimate density, hence resulting in biased and unrealistic estimates when compared with field density estimates (Table 1).

Our analyses were based on RedList global abundance estimates, as thoroughly described in the original manuscript. The question is not whether the RedList has limitations but whether there is any better alternative for the scope of our study and whether the result we get is robust. The RedList dataset has limitations and biases but is the only global dataset of its kind and has been updated and improved over many years. We used this dataset to provide a biomass estimate for all wild mammals combined. While estimates might have a high uncertainty at the single-species level, it is significantly reduced when summed across many species, as we report. The many challenges of estimating the global abundance of single species were addressed in our work, as well as in subsequent commentaries (3, 4).

The RL dataset includes an overrepresentation of threatened species (60% vs. 27% of all mammals). The authors control for this bias by including RL categories as models' predictors. However, no RL criteria relate to density, with ~80% mammal species threatened due to small or decreasing ranges.

We acknowledged these biases extensively in our manuscript (Materials and Methods, “Inferring the biomass of wild land mammal species lacking global population reports”). Using RedList categories, which classify species according to the risk of global extinction as a model predictor, could help reduce some of the bias of estimating total abundances of species at different levels of risk of extinction. The RedList category was also deemed relevant as a model feature based on the model fit.

Finally, model extrapolations are based on data heavily biased towards ungulates (40% vs. 4.7% of all mammals) while not controlling for phylogenetic relatedness but reassigning species to other taxonomic order for model predictions.

Model predictors include range size, body mass, Red List category, phylogenetic order and trophic level. Due to the lack of representation for some phylogenetic orders in the population abundance dataset ≈500 species were assigned the phylogenetic orders of a close relative. The full description can be found under the “Model features preprocessing and model parameters” subsection in the original manuscript SI.

While our dataset is biased towards large-bodied species, due to their visibility among other factors. We applied multiple sensitivity analyses, which are also discussed at length in the discussion section:

*“We find that most of the biomass of wild land mammals is concentrated in relatively abundant, large-ranged and large-body-sized species. Although reports are available for many large-bodied species, we estimate that only ≈55% of the biomass of land mammals is represented by species with global population reports, which is concentrated in a small subset of 6% of species that tend to have large body weight. This calls for more species-specific global abundance assessments, as some of the highest mass contributors (e.g., the common warthog, *Phacochoerus africanus*) still lack species-specific global abundance reports, and were, therefore, estimated in this work. A specific assessment of their global abundance would provide a more accurate view on significant species in terms of overall biomass, and on the*

distribution of mass across species, clades, and geographical regions. In addition, global abundance reports for widely distributed small-sized mammals, such as many bat species (Chiroptera), are lacking; thus, their global biomass estimates contain a high degree of uncertainty. Measuring the abundance of these small species is challenging, but could improve the global quantification of mammalian biomass. Since the methods used in this study are both easily repeatable and readily scalable, additional mammal population reports can easily be incorporated to improve our estimates.”

Consequently, predicted density estimates by Greenspoon et al. (1) deviate substantially from published estimates obtained in hundreds of field studies (5) (median absolute orders of magnitude deviation=0.64, 95%=0.06-2.5, N=159, Fig. 1a) and are on average underestimated by 3 folds (median orders of magnitude deviation=-0.47).

Santini et al. compare what they call “predicted density estimates” to field studies but this in our perspective is akin to comparing apples to oranges as inferred global mean densities are not comparable to field studies in sites that are often selected for convenience and ease of counting. They additionally suggest that multiplying local densities from their published dataset (5) with range size provides more realistic abundance estimates. We considered this approach in the past and discussed it with Prof. Santini but decided not to pursue it due to several biases it contains that are especially problematic for the overall aim of quantifying global biomass. Population densities vary dramatically across a species’ range, and researchers mostly study animal populations where they are abundant (6). Consequently, locally measured population densities tend to be biased towards maximal densities (6) and are unrepresentative of species’ mean densities across their entire extent of suitable habitat (6, 7). The approach suggested by Santini et al. seems to disregard this strong, and well-known relationship. We therefore contend that their method is likely to grossly inflate species global population sizes (see examples below).

Additionally, the Santini et al. 2022 dataset contains density measurements conducted between 1970-2020, during which many populations suffered sharp declines (8) and is therefore expected to overestimate the global abundances of species that experienced decline.

This may have profound effects on global estimates (Fig 1b), leading to a potential underestimation of biomass of ~5.5-fold difference (9.4 Mt vs. 52 Mt for 159 species).

Santini et al., essentially suggest that it is more reasonable to simply multiply locally measured field densities with range size (which was approximated using the extent of suitable habitat, to achieve total population size) than using expert assessments.

We replicated the analysis suggested by Santini et al., and find that ≈85% of the 52 Mt inferred by Santini et al. is concentrated in 10 species. These 10 species are all large-bodied, highly monitored and surveyed over large areas to produce expert-based abundance assessments. It is unlikely that extrapolated local densities produce more reliable estimates of the total population size than expert assessments, as shown in Table 1. For example, the method suggested by Santini et al. infers ≈500 million Eastern gray kangaroos, 20 times more than the

number of people in Australia. Australian authorities estimate that there are ≈ 20 million Eastern gray kangaroos, as we describe in the SI of the original manuscript. Similarly, the method suggested by Santini et al. produces population abundance estimates an order of magnitude higher than expert assessments for two of the world's most monitored species, estimating ≈ 20 million blue wildebeest (*Connochaetes taurinus*) compared to ≈ 2 million by expert assessment and ≈ 1 million white rhinoceros (*Ceratotherium simum*) compared to ≈ 20 thousand by expert assessment.

Furthermore, we could not replicate the results of 7 of the top 10 marine mammals' biomass due to inconsistent use of RL data (Table 1).

Extracting data manually from heterogeneous texts for ≈ 5000 mammal species is a task that can contain some misinterpretations and manual errors.

While rechecking values following this correspondence we found a few minor errors in the total population within those species.

The total effect of all corrections on total wild marine mammal biomass is negligible ($<1\%$). We corrected the values in the paper gitlab repository.

The uncertainty computed by (1) is based on several expert-based intervals and applied to all species, including marine mammals for which estimates of variability are available from literature and the RL but were not used (6). This results in a gross underestimation of the uncertainty around the global biomass prediction (Table 1).

Santini et al seem to have misinterpreted the conservative approach we took which aimed to avoid under-estimation of uncertainty. We analyzed and collected uncertainty reports for species with the largest mass contribution for which confidence intervals were available and found that all of them were smaller than two-fold. To be conservative, for each of the species with reported population abundances, we set 95% confidence intervals of two-fold above and below the estimated values. We calculated the final uncertainty as described in our manuscript:

“The total biomass of wild mammals is the sum of estimated biomass for each mammal species. Population size reports for most species did not report the uncertainty. We therefore analyzed and collected the available uncertainty reports for the species with the largest mass contribution for which CIs were available (SI Appendix, Table S2) and found that all of them were smaller than twofold. To be conservative, for each of the species with reported population abundances, we set a 95% CI within an upper and lower bound of twofold above and below the estimated size. Due to lack of better data, we assumed that uncertainties in the population reports are log-normally distributed. For species lacking population reports, we used bootstrapping based on 1,000 runs of our model to establish a 95% CI (see Inferring the Biomass of Wild Land Mammal Species Lacking Global Population Reports for a full description of the models). From each distribution, we extracted the mean and random errors (the means and medians of these distributions were almost identical). The uncertainty ranges for the total biomass of wild land and marine mammals were calculated summing the lower or upper bounds of the 95% CIs for each such distribution. We used this sum of bounds of the 95% CIs to account for both random,

and possible systematic, errors, as this way of summing includes possible correlations between the underlying statistical errors.”

While estimating biomass globally provides important insights, we call for a more careful consideration of data quality and consistency, and a more robust reporting of uncertainty. We recommend fitting models on empirically-derived field density estimates while controlling for phylogeny, environmental variables, and inconsistent sampling methods (e.g. 5, 7). Uncertainty should be derived directly from the statistical predictive error and, when possible, also from the underlying data. Alternatively, mechanistic eco-physiological models can be used to estimate global biomass following trait-based theory and validated with independent data (7).

Fitting models on empirically-derived field density estimates to achieve global abundance estimates requires ample data. This was, for example, recently achieved for only two feline species (9) using a dedicated study for species with especially ample data. This approach cannot be applied more comprehensively with current datasets.

Deriving uncertainty directly from the underlying data is impossible across ≈5000 wild mammal species. We analyzed and collected uncertainty reports for species with the largest mass contribution for which CIs were available (SI Appendix, Table S2) and found that all of them were smaller than twofold. To be conservative, for each of the species with reported population abundances, we set a 95% CI within an upper and lower bound of twofold above and below the estimated values.

Table S1. Point-by-point reply to Table 1, Santini et al., 2023.

Category	Examples	Implications
<p>Sum of inconsistently estimated population sizes</p> <p>Population estimates were taken from expert assessments.</p> <p>We further clarify in the columns to the right.</p>	<p>Estimates for <i>Odocoileus virginianus</i> come from US wildlife state agencies using not transparently reported survey methods. Some states include both white-tailed and mule deers (e.g. Colorado).</p> <p>Colorado alone, which constitutes only ≈2% of estimated white-tailed deer population in the USA, contains mule deer estimates as well. These estimates are conducted by state wildlife agencies.</p> <p>Canada population estimated by direct extrapolation from US numbers based on percent range area. Latin American population based on average density of 1</p>	<p>Inconsistent estimates introduce biases in the population density calculation and model predictions.</p> <p>In this case biomass is underestimated by -60% (2.7Mt vs 8.2Mt).</p> <p>It seems unlikely that a dedicated analysis by experts from the US wildlife state agencies is less accurate than a simple extrapolation of local densities for a species inhabiting multiple habitats and climatic zones over a huge range.</p> <p>Nevertheless, there is still a</p>

	<p>ind/km2.</p> <p>These extrapolations are detailed in the SI section and based on our correspondence with Dr. Kurt C. VerCauteren, the lead author on the report we cite, “Regulated commercial harvest to manage overabundant white-tailed deer: An idea to consider?”, Wildl. Soc. Bull. 35, 185–194 (2011). Dr. Kurt C. VerCauteren is an expert on white-tailed deer in North America.</p> <p>This figure yields a density estimate of 3.4 ind/km2 (8). Field estimates are 3x higher on average (5): M=10.2 ind/km2; IQR=2.177-20.5; N=38.</p> <p>We reiterate that we did not intend or claim to use population-size data to infer field densities of specific mammal species.</p>	<p>significant overlap in the confidence intervals of the Santini et al. and our estimates.</p>
<p>Population estimated from mean density, which divided by a different area leads to a different density estimate</p> <p>Population is estimated directly from RedList total population abundance estimates for species where such data is available.</p> <p>We further clarify in the columns to the right.</p>	<p>The RL estimates a total population size of ~104K for the orangutan (<i>Pongo pygmaeus</i>) by multiplying a mean density of 0.67 ind/km2 by 155K km2. Greenspoon et al. divided 104K individuals by a habitat area of >82K km2 obtaining an estimate of 1.26 ind/km2, almost twice the original density estimate.</p> <p>We use the total abundance of orangutans, not the density, in our final biomass estimate.</p> <p>We reiterate that we did not intend or claim to use population-size data to infer field densities of specific mammal species. While the density values we derived are different from those used to derive the total abundance,</p> <p>Nevertheless, there is still an overlap between the density value used as a model input and the density value assigned by the IUCN. We set a 95% CI within an upper and lower bound of twofold above and below the estimated values, as</p>	<p>Introduction of biases in the population density calculation and model predictions.</p> <p>While dividing orangutan estimated population by the extent of suitable habitat might have resulted in densities higher than estimated by experts, we applied a machine learning algorithm to infer the global biomass of species for which no population reports were available. This method is relatively robust and not heavily influenced by outliers.</p> <p>We performed multiple sensitivity analyses on our main result, the estimated global biomass of wild mammals.</p>

	described in the manuscript.	
<p>Density obtained dividing the population size reported by the RL by area does not match the density reported in the same RL report</p> <p>Locally-measured population densities are unrepresentative of species' mean densities across their entire extent of suitable habitat.</p> <p>We further clarify in the columns on the right.</p>	<p>The RL reports a total population of 323-955 for the Cozumel raccoon (<i>Procyon pygmaeus</i>), the midrange is 639 but Greenspoon et al. reported 465.</p> <p>Indeed in this case there seems to have been a typo in the value used. The effect on all our results is negligible.</p> <p>The latter was divided by the habitat area resulting in 1.48 ind/km². However, the RL reports that the species' population density ranges between 12–112 ind/km².</p> <p>Total population was calculated using capture-recapture methods.</p> <p>While measured field densities are 12–112 ind/km², these numbers clearly do not reflect the mean density over the entire extent of suitable habitat, which we used to approximate mammal ranges (extent of suitable habitat).</p>	<p>The mismatch suggests the approach taken is flawed and can lead to important deviations from known density estimates, which are propagated through the models and predictions.</p> <p>We reiterate that we did not intend or claim to use population-size data to infer field densities of specific mammal species.</p> <p>We applied a machine learning algorithm to infer the global biomass of species for which no population reports were available. This method is relatively robust and not heavily influenced by outliers.</p> <p>We performed multiple sensitivity analyses on our main result, the estimated global biomass of wild mammals.</p>
<p>Dividing population size by habitat area result in unrealistic population density estimates.</p> <p>We clarify this misunderstanding in the columns on the right.</p>	<p>The mountain pigmy possum (<i>Burramys parvus</i>) is estimated to have a density of 2.69 ind/km², field density estimates are substantially higher: M=890 ind/km², IQR=510-1335; N=11 (5).</p> <p>Total population was calculated in a dedicated 2008 analysis by RedList experts. The values suggested by Santini et al were measured in a single site in the year 1988.</p> <p>The Tibetan antelope (<i>Pantholops hodgsonii</i>) is estimated to have a density of 1437 ind/km², field density estimates are M=4.3 in/km²; IQR=1.7-6.8; N=11 (5).</p> <p>The Tibetan antelope is found in high mountains and semi-desert of the Tibetan Plateau. However, its list</p>	<p>Severe under or overestimation of mammal biomass.</p> <p>We reiterate that we did not intend or claim to use population-size data to infer field densities of specific mammal species.</p> <p>We applied a machine learning algorithm to infer the global biomass of species for which no population reports were available. This method is relatively robust and not heavily influenced by outliers.</p> <p>We performed multiple sensitivity analyses on our main result, the estimated global biomass of wild mammals.</p>

	<p>of suitable habitats in the RedList dataset only includes temperate grassland and pasture land. As we use the intersection between suitable habitats and EOO to estimate the Extent of Suitable Habitats (ESH) for each species, the estimated ESH is significantly smaller in this case than the antelope's area or occupancy.</p> <p>However, while the density values we derived are likely too high, we use the total abundance of antelopes, not the density, in our final biomass estimate.</p>	
<p>Inconsistent use of RL reported populations, sometime taken from the description, sometimes from the reported total, sometimes neither</p> <p>We extracted total population values from RedList population description.</p> <p>We clarify this misunderstanding in the columns on the right.</p>	<p>12M individuals for the Crabeater seal (<i>Lobodon carcinophaga</i>) in the SI, 10M in Table 2, RL reports 4-8M;</p> <p>The value 12M appears in an unused old data file that was now removed from the gitlab repository. RedList reports 8 million individuals in total, this is one of the species for which the values were corrected. The total effect of all corrections on marine mammal biomass is negligible (<1%).</p> <p>27.5K for the Blue whale (<i>Balaenoptera musculus</i>), RL reports 10-25K including the smaller pygmy blue whale and juveniles;</p> <p>This was a typo in the curated values, which we now corrected in the gitlab support files. The total effect of all corrections on marine mammal biomass is negligible (<1%).</p> <p>200K for the Minke whale (<i>Balaenoptera acutorostrata</i>), RL reports 187K;</p> <p>RL reports 200K individuals (see link "Assessment Information in detail") and not 187K. However, we used this opportunity to update the values to 500K according to more recent data from the International Whaling</p>	<p>Impossible to reproduce the results because of the inconsistent use of RL estimates.</p> <p>Extracting data from heterogenous texts for ≈5000 mammal species is a difficult task and bound to contain some manual errors.</p> <p>While rechecking values following this correspondence we did find a few minor errors in the total population within the top 10 species. We therefore corrected the values accordingly. The corrected top 10 table is available in our gitlab.</p> <p>The total effect of all corrections on marine mammal biomass is negligible (<1%).</p>

	<p>Commission which contains a report for total population (including immature individuals). The total effect of all corrections on marine mammal biomass is negligible (<1%).</p> <p>35K for the Bowhead whale (<i>Balaena mysticetus</i>), RL reports >25K.</p> <p>This was a mistake in summing the curated values, which we now corrected. The total effect of all corrections on marine mammal biomass is negligible (<1%).</p> <p>54K for <i>Hypogeomys antimena</i>, RL reports 5036 mature individuals.</p> <p>Our data was curated in late 2019 as detailed in the paper. <i>Hypogeomys antimena</i> abundance has since been updated (2022) by RL experts, the original values extracted can be found in our gitlab repository.</p>	
<p>Inconsistent inclusion of juveniles in total populations with use of adult body mass</p> <p>There is no inconsistency. We use total population values and mean body mass (corrected for the inclusion of juveniles).</p> <p>We clarify this misunderstanding in the columns on the right.</p>	<p>Methods do not report the juvenile/adult ratio used for marine mammals nor account for differences in body mass between juveniles and adults. Juveniles were added to the RL estimates of adults for Fin whale (<i>Balaenoptera physalus</i>), Sperm whale (<i>Physeter macrocephalus</i>) and Blue whale (<i>Balaenoptera musculus</i>), but not to the other top 10 marine mammals calculations, even though RL clearly reports adult-only populations.</p> <p>We extracted total population values from RedList population description. Extracting data from long text for ≈5000 mammal species is a difficult task and bound to contain some manual errors.</p> <p>While rechecking values following this correspondence we did find a few minor errors in the total population within the top 10 species. We therefore corrected the values</p>	<p>Excluding juveniles leads to biomass under-estimation whereas using adult body mass for juveniles leads to over-estimation</p> <p>There seems to be a misreading of our methods.</p> <p>For marine mammals, we used mean, and not adult, body mass estimates as calculated by Trites and Pauly, 1998 (10).</p>

	<p>accordingly. The corrected top 10 table is available in our gitlab.</p> <p>The total effect of all corrections on marine mammal biomass is negligible (<1%).</p>	
<p>Under-estimation of uncertainty</p> <p>There seems to be a misreading of our methods.</p> <p>We clarify this misunderstanding in the columns on the right.</p>	<p>Uncertainty in the RL is expert-based and not meant to represent the real uncertainty around the total estimate. Population size of mature individuals of the African buffalo (<i>Syncerus caffer</i>) between 398K-401K (<1% error). However, the RL clearly states that while some regional estimates are available through aerial counts, the total estimate is highly uncertain since estimates from many regions are absent or biased (9).</p> <p>We analyzed and collected uncertainty reports for species with the largest mass contribution for which CIs were available (SI Appendix, Table S2) and found that all of them were smaller than twofold. To be conservative, for each of the species with reported population abundances, we set a 95% CI within an upper and lower bound of twofold above and below the estimated values.</p>	<p>Uncertainty of the total population size based on many independent estimates is expected to be much higher than in individual estimates. This approach leads to severe under-estimation of uncertainty of the global biomass prediction.</p> <p>Sanitini et al. seem to have misinterpreted the conservative approach we took. We used bootstrapping based on 1,000 runs of our model to establish a 95% CI, as described in our point-by point response above as well as in the “Final Biomass Estimate and Uncertainty” section under “Methods” in the original manuscript.</p>

Table S2. We replicated the analysis presented in Fig. 1B by Santini et al.. Santini et al. inferred the total biomass of 158 species from their local population density measurements, arriving at 55 Mt. However, ≈85% of said biomass is concentrated in 10 species, all of which are large bodied species surveyed over large areas for abundance assessments by experts, where it is unreasonable to assume that local densities extrapolated naively are more reliable than expert assessments

Common name	Binomial	Population (millions)		Biomass (Mt)	
		Suggested by Santini et al.	Reported in Greenspoon et al.	Suggested by Santini et al.	Reported in Greenspoon et al.
Eastern gray kangaroo	<i>Macropus giganteus</i>	540	22	14.5	0.6
White-tailed deer	<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	130	45	8.2	2.7
Plains zebra	<i>Equus quagga</i>	21	0.5	6.7	0.2
Blue wildebeest	<i>Connochaetes taurinus</i>	28	1.6	4.4	0.2
African buffalo	<i>Syncerus caffer</i>	7.4	0.6	3.5	0.3
Nilgai	<i>Boselaphus tragocamelus</i>	21	0.1	3.1	<0.1
White rhinoceros	<i>Ceratotherium simum</i>	1.4	<0.1	2.5	<0.1
African forest elephant	<i>Loxodonta cyclotis</i>	0.3	0.1	1	0.3
Asian elephant	<i>Elephas maximus</i>	0.4	<0.1	0.9	0.1
Common wallaroo	<i>Macropus robustus</i>	42	4.5	0.9	0.1
Total		≈800	≈80	46	4.5

Top contributors to biomass as inferred in the approach by Santini et al are inflated 10-100 fold compared to consensus estimates by experts

Figure 1. We replicated the analysis presented in Fig. 1B by Santini et al.. Santini et al. inferred the total biomass of 158 species from their local population density measurements, arriving at 55 Mt. However, ≈85% of said biomass is concentrated in 10 species. These 10 species are all large-bodied, highly monitored and surveyed over large areas to produce expert-based abundance assessments. It is unreasonable to assume that local densities extrapolated naïvely are more reliable than expert assessments. Using the method suggested by Santini et al, the estimated number means that Eastern gray kangaroos outnumber humans in Australia 20 to 1.

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